

4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) frag. 20 and PAM 43.221 top, second from left (Exod 3:18-21)

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The photograph PAM 43.221 contains the conglomerate of fragments which together form 4Q31 cols. I and II, and a range of other Pentateuchal fragments, most of which have been transferred to other Museum Plates. The top left of the photograph shows 4Q5 frag. 2 (presently IAA Plate 420, Frag. 4) and second to left a fragment which seems to be unpublished, and which plausibly should be assigned to 4Q1 and aligned to the left of 4Q1 frag. 20 lines 1-2, thus providing a few more letters of Exod 3:18-20. I am not aware of the present location of the PAM 43.221 fragment.

The following image shows at the right 4Q1 frag. 20, at the left the PAM 43.221 fragment.

Fragments captured from

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284250>
and <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284669>
Israel Antiquities Authority, photos Najib Anton Albina

These fragments may be transcribed as follows:

[ליהו[ה אלה]נו ואני יד[עתי]	1
בי[ד חזק]ה ושל[חתי את]	2
בקר[בו וא]חרי	3
[תלכו]ן]	4

References:

Edition 4Q1: James R. Davila, "1. 4QGen-Exoda," in *Qumran Cave 4 VII: Genesis to Numbers*, ed. Eugene Ulrich and Frank Moore Cross; Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XII (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1994)

Other recent identifications of 4Q1 fragments:

- Join of 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) frags. 5, 38, 41, and 46 (Genesis 36). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5542246>
- Join of 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) frags. 5 and 46. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5528230>
- Join of 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) frags. 26 and 48. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5528237>
- Join of 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) frags. 9 and 47. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5525212>
- PAM 43.689 frag. 33 (IAA Plate 90 frags. 86-88) Identified as a 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) fragment (Gen 32:29-30?). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5503557>
- Three Additional 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) Fragments. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4302465>

See also:

- The Qumran 4Q1 and 4Q9 Fragments without Photograph in DJD XII. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5806686>
- 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) Frag. 60 + 4Q49 (4QJudg^a). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5114482>